

Electrochemical reactions at sacrificial electrode. Part-XVIII : Synthesis of coordination compounds of zinc(II) alkoxides

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Abstract : Electrochemical oxidation of sacrificial zinc anode in alcohols containing a ligand (1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridyl) yields coordination compounds of zinc(II) alkoxides. The products are identified by elemental analysis and infrared spectral studies. These are polymeric in nature like their parent zinc(II) alkoxides. Current efficiencies of most of these systems are quite high.

Keywords : Zinc(II) alkoxides, synthesis, electrochemical reactions, sacrificial electrodes.

Introduction

Electrochemical synthetic technique provides a single step, direct and eco-friendly route for the synthesis of pure organic¹⁻⁵ and inorganic⁶⁻¹⁰ compounds in high yield under ambient conditions without the use of hazardous reagents. The technique is highly selective. Recently we reported¹¹ the electrochemical synthesis of zinc(II) alkoxides. Alkoxides, generally do not form coordination compounds as the coordination sphere of central metal atom in metal alkoxides is saturated through alkoxy bridging, therefore, it was considered worthwhile to synthesize the coordination compounds of zinc(II) alkoxides by electrochemical method.

Experimental

Reagents and solvent : Acetonitrile was dried over phosphorus pentoxide and then fractionally double distilled. Alcohols were treated with dry magnesium metal and small amount of iodine and then were distilled. Tetrabutylammonium chloride was crystallised from conductivity water and dried under reduced pressure at 100 °C.

Procedure and technique : Electrochemical reactions of various alcohols (2.0 mL) methanol, ethanol, propan-1-ol, butan-1-ol, pentan-1-ol, hexan-1-ol, heptan-1-ol, octan-1-ol, nonan-1-ol, decan-1-ol, dodecan-1-ol, 3-methylhexan-3-ol or 1-(dimethylamino)propan-2-ol) in

acetonitrile (250 mL) alongwith ligand (1.0 g) (1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridyl) using tetrabutylammonium chloride (1.0 g) as supporting electrolyte have been conducted in a H-type pyrex glass cell having two compartments separated through sintered glass disc of G-3 porosity (A number of experiments have been conducted in order to check the effect of chain length on the solubility of product of these systems). Both the compartments were fitted with guard tubes. Zinc plate ($2 \times 10 \times 0.2 \text{ cm}^3$) was used as anode and platinum foil ($1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$) was used as cathode. Direct current was obtained from electrophoresis power supply. Solid products separated in the anode compartment were isolated.

Melting points of these products were determined by using an electrical device, which was adjusted so that the temperature rose by five degrees per minute during melting point measurements.

For the determination of zinc contents, a known amount of the product was heated to dryness with fuming nitric acid four times. The dry mass obtained was dissolved in 5 mL of water and 3 drops of hydrochloric acid. The solution was boiled and diluted to a volume of 25 mL. Zinc contents in this solution were determined volumetrically by oxine method¹². Microanalyses for carbon and hydrogen in these products have also been conducted. Infrared spectra of these products were recorded with Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, RXI, using potassium bromide pellets in the region of $4000\text{--}450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Current efficiencies of all these systems have been determined by electrolyzing the reaction mixture in the above said manner for two hours at a constant current of 20 mA. The solution was stirred thoroughly during the progress of the reaction. The whole contents of anode compartment were transferred to a round bottomed flask alongwith the washings of the compartment. The solution was concentrated in film evaporator. The contents of round-bottomed flask alongwith the washings were transferred into a beaker and were heated to dryness. Zinc content in the dry mass was determined by oxine method¹² as detailed above. The ratio of experimental zinc contents to theoretical zinc contents gives the current efficiency.

Results and discussion

Zinc(II) alkoxides reported¹¹ earlier were refluxed with 1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridyl in different solvents such as methanol, ethanol, acetonitrile and benzene for more than 48 h in order to prepare coordination compounds of these alkoxides. Elemental analysis and infrared spectral studies of these products revealed that the ligand molecules could not be attached to zinc in these alkoxides. It was, therefore, thought worthwhile that the ligand may be added to these alkoxides before they form alkoxy bridges and get polymerised. Therefore, in addition to alcohols and supporting electrolyte, ligand was also added to the reaction mixture before it was electrolysed at zinc anode and platinum cathode. Potential across the electrodes was adjusted so that a current of 20 mA passed through the cell. The solution was stirred continuously during the electrolysis. The electrolytic cell can be represented as :

where, $\text{Zn}_{(+)}$ represents sacrificial zinc anode. $\text{Pt}_{(-)}$ represents platinum cathode and L represents ligand (1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridyl).

The electrolysis has been carried out for ten hours in order to obtain sufficient amount of the product. The solid products separated in the anode compartment were filtered, washed with acetonitrile and dry ether and then dried under reduced pressure.

The solid electrochemical products obtained from anode compartment are quite stable and are not much affected by air and moisture. These products are insoluble in commonly used organic solvents like dimethyl sulphoxide, *N,N*-dimethyl formamide, benzene, chloroform, metha-

nol etc. As a result, their molecular weights could not be determined by conventional methods. All these products do not melt upto 300 °C but decompose around 200 °C as evident from the change in colour of these products around this temperature.

Contents of zinc, carbon and hydrogen in these electrochemical products reveal 2 : 1 : 1 stoichiometry of alcohol, zinc and ligand respectively. The analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

Table 1. Current efficiencies of electrochemical reactions of various alcohol + ligand systems at zinc anode at different intervals of time

System	Time (min)	Current efficiency (Gram equivalent/Faraday)
Methanol + 1,10-phenanthroline	120	0.90
Ethanol + 1,10-phenanthroline	120	0.90
Propan-1-ol + 1,10-phenanthroline	120	0.92
Butan-1-ol + 1,10-phenanthroline	120	0.89
Pentan-1-ol + 1,10-phenanthroline	120	0.88
Hexan-1-ol + 1,10-phenanthroline	120	0.94
Heptan-1-ol + 1,10-phenanthroline	15	0.97
	30	0.62
	60	0.51
	120	0.41
Octan-1-ol + 1,10-phenanthroline	15	0.91
	30	0.70
	60	0.61
	120	0.59
Nonan-1-ol + 1,10-phenanthroline	15	0.80
	30	0.60
	60	0.52
	120	0.42
Decan-1-ol + 1,10-phenanthroline	15	0.80
	30	0.69
	60	0.59
	120	0.48
Dodecan-1-ol + 1,10-phenanthroline	120	0.70
3-Methylhexan-3-ol + 1,10-phenanthroline	120	0.89

Table-1 (contd.)

1-(Dimethylamino)propan-2-ol + 1,10-phenanthroline	120	0.95
Methanol + 2,2'- bipyridyl	120	0.91
Ethanol + 2,2'- bipyridyl	120	0.89
Propan-1-ol + 2,2'- bipyridyl	120	0.84
Butan-1-ol + 2,2'- bipyridyl	120	0.87
Pentan-1-ol + 2,2'- bipyridyl	120	0.80
Hexan-1-ol + 2,2'- bipyridyl	120	0.72
Heptan-1-ol + 2,2'- bipyridyl	120	0.97
Octan-1-ol + 2,2'- bipyridyl	120	0.65
Nonan-1-ol + 2,2'- bipyridyl	120	0.97
Decan-1-ol + 2,2'- bipyridyl	120	0.97
Dodecan-1-ol + 2,2'- bipyridyl	120	0.63
3-Methylhexan-3-ol + 2,2'- bipyridyl	120	0.97
1-(Dimethylamino)propan-2-ol + 2,2'- bipyridyl	120	0.92

Infrared spectra of these products do not show any absorption band corresponding to hydroxyl group^{13,14}, but show characteristics bands in the regions of 465–450, 1160–1020 and 1626–1428 cm^{-1} . The bands present in the region of 465–450 cm^{-1} may be attributed to $\nu(\text{Zn-O})$ mode^{15,17-20} and bands appearing in the region of 1160–1020 cm^{-1} are attributed to $\nu(\text{C-O})\text{Zn}$ mode^{16-18,20}. Two distinct absorption bands are present in the region of 1160–1020 cm^{-1} in all these products.

The presence of $\nu(\text{Zn-O})$ and $\nu(\text{C-O})\text{Zn}$ band and absence of $\nu(\text{O-H})$ band in the products indicate that the proton of these alcohols have been replaced by anodic zinc. Comparison of the infrared spectral data with those of the parent alkoxides¹¹ reveals that in the present products the $\nu(\text{C-O})\text{Zn}$ and $\nu(\text{Zn-O})$ modes appear in slightly higher region. The shift of these bands may be attributed to the coordination of ligand to the zinc(II) alkoxides.

The bands present in the region of 1626–1418 cm^{-1} may be attributed to $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{C})$ and $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ bands of the ligand molecules¹⁴ as these bands were not observed in the parent alkoxides. Comparison of these bands with those of pure ligand reveals that these bands in the present products appear in a slightly lower region. Presence of these bands and their shift towards lower region also support the coordination of the ligands to the alkoxides.

Survey of literature reveals^{16-18,20} that two types of $\nu(\text{C-O})\text{Zn}$ bands appear for metal alkoxides. The bands in the region of 1060–1020 cm^{-1} are assigned to bridged alkoxide groups and those in the region of 1160–1060 cm^{-1} are due to terminal alkoxide groups. In the present studies $\nu(\text{C-O})\text{Zn}$ bands are observed in both the regions. Appearance of $\nu(\text{C-O})\text{Zn}$ stretching vibrations in 1090–1020 cm^{-1} region indicates the polymeric nature of these products like the parent zinc(II) alkoxides. Polymeric nature of the products is also supported by high melting point and insoluble behaviour of these compounds.

Current efficiencies of all these systems have been determined and are summarised in Table 1. Perusal of Table 1 reveals that the current efficiencies of most of these systems are quite high except those of heptan-1-ol + 1,10-phenanthroline, octan-1-ol + 1,10-phenanthroline, nonan-1-ol + 1,10-phenanthroline and decan-1-ol + 1,10-phenanthroline systems. High current efficiencies of these systems reveal that the reactions leading to the formation of coordination compounds of zinc(II) alkoxides are the predominant reactions of these systems. The reaction scheme can be written as :

At cathode :

At anode :

In order to throw light on the reason of low current efficiencies of the said systems, the current efficiencies of these systems have been determined at different intervals of time. All the relevant data are recorded in Table 1. Perusal of Table 1 reveals that current efficiencies of these systems are very high initially but decrease with the passage of time. The decrease in current efficiencies with time may be due to the fact that the reaction product of these systems sticks to the surface of anode and thus form a protective layer on its surface, which inhibits the further dissolution of zinc. Survey of literature²¹⁻²⁴ reveals that many organic compounds act as corrosion inhibitors

by forming a protective layer at sacrificial electrodes. Recently Banait *et al.*¹¹ reported similar behaviour of hexan-1-ol, heptan-1-ol and octan-1-ol at sacrificial zinc anode.

The electrochemical method provides a single step, simple and direct route for the preparation of coordination compounds of zinc(II) alkoxides, which could not be prepared by simple chemical methods. The products are obtained in high yield and are pure.

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